

Development of Antimicrobial Textiles using Neem Seed Extract - A Sustainable Approach

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Abstract;

This study focused on the extraction of natural antimicrobial agent from neem seed (Azadirachta indica) to apply it on cotton, polyester and linen fabrics. Aqueous neem-seed extract had been prepared by decoction method and major compounds were identified by phytochemical analysis. The neem seed extract of optimized concentration with cross-linking agent was applied on to fabrics by pad-dry-cure method. The finished fabrics were analyzed for antimicrobial activity against gram-positive and gram-negative bacteria. The results show that the neem treated linen fabric has the best antimicrobial activity when compared to neem-treated cotton and polyester fabrics. FTIR spectrum of the treated fabric samples confirmed the presence of bioactive compounds in the finished fabric. The study suggests that neem seed extract could be a less expensive, non-toxic and effective alternative to traditional antimicrobial agents for fabric treatment.

Keywords: antimicrobial agent, cotton, decoction method, linen, neem seed extract, phytochemical analysis, polyester

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1. Introduction

Antimicrobial textiles are gaining popularity due to the increasing demand for products that offer protection against bacteria and other microorganisms. The use of natural antimicrobial agents in the textile industry is a sustainable approach that can offer an eco-friendly alternative to traditional chemical-based treatments. The antimicrobial qualities of Neem oil, when combined with other herbal oils like Clove, Tulsi, and Karanga, have been harnessed to apply an antimicrobial finish to cotton textiles.

The Neem tree (*Azadirachta indica*), belonging to the Meliaceae (Mahogany) family, stands out as one of the most abundant sources of bioactive compounds in the Indian subcontinent. Indian farmers extensively utilize Neem leaf extract to safeguard their crops against pests and fungi, owing to its reputed antibacterial properties. Earlier studies reveal that neem seed or bark extract with a crosslinking agent was applied on to cotton fabric by conventional or microwave-curing methods [1]. The use of natural products for imparting antibacterial properties to textiles is gaining importance due to concerns over the environmental impact and potential health hazards associated with synthetic chemical. Attempts are being made to develop effective and long lasting antimicrobial finishes on textiles as textiles can harbor harmful bacteria causing skin infections and other illnesses [2, 3].

The traditional chemical treatments can have negative environmental impacts and may not be suitable for certain applications and thus making natural extracts as a promising alternative. Many studies reported the effectiveness of plant extracts in preventing bacterial growth on fabrics [4]. It was claimed that the bioactive constituents in neem are less toxic to warm-blooded animals like human [5]. In the recent years, neem extract has gained attention for its potential use in textile applications due to its antimicrobial, antiviral, and antifungal properties [6-8].

The natural fabric treated with neem, combined with citric acid, exhibits superior antimicrobial activity compared to the fabric treated with acetic acid. Increasing the concentration of the neem leaf extracted solution enhances the effectiveness of the antimicrobial activity on the cotton fabric. Among the various concentrations of the

extracted solution, the treatment using a 7g/l concentration, along with citric acid, yields the highest level of antimicrobial activity on the treated natural fabric [9]. Earlier studies disclose the use of neem for the functional finishing of textile materials [10, 11]. Phytochemical analysis is used to identify and quantify the chemical compounds in plants, providing insights into their medicinal and nutritional value, and guiding the development of drugs and natural products. Neem leaf extracts comprise organic compounds such as nimbidin, nimbolide, mahmoodin, margolone, margolonone, and isomargolonon, all of which exhibit notable antibiotic properties [12]. Research investigating the antimicrobial efficacy of flax reveals impressive zones of inhibition against both gram-positive (*S. pyogenes*) and gram-negative (*K. aerogenes*) bacteria surrounding the treated fabric [13]. Neem essential oil nanoparticles were formulated using nano-emulsion and ionic gelation technique and applied to cotton and polyester fabric to give them antibacterial properties [14].

2. Materials and Methods

The woven textile materials selected for the study included 100% cotton, 100% polyester and 100% linen fabrics. These natural and synthetic fabrics were used in various applications such as clothing, home textiles, and upholstery. The specifications of fabrics sourced from local market given below in Table 1.

Table 1: Fabrics specifications

Property	Cotton	Polyester	Linen
Weave	Plain	Plain	Plain
EPI	117	150	90
PPI	98	130	75
GSM	140	140	140
Thickness (mm)	0.32	0.28	0.32
Warp Count	60s Ne	45 denier	25 Nm
Weft Count	60s Ne	45 denier	25 Nm

The active ingredient used in the antimicrobial finishing is the kernel with the coat of the neem seed. It has already been well documented that the extract of the neem seeds has antimicrobial properties. In addition, neem extract is also known to repel insects, making it a popular natural insecticide.

Flow Chart for the Methodology

2.1 Preparation of Neem Seed Extract

The fresh neem seeds were obtained by squeezing out the skin of the neem fruits collected from neem trees of southern India. Neem seeds were washed thoroughly two to three times with distilled water. Then the seeds were shadow dried at room temperature (~30°C) for five to seven days. After complete drying, the seeds were crushed into a coarse powder by using the grinder.

Figure 1 - Neem seed Powder

The active compounds from dried neem seeds were extracted using an aqueous extraction method known as the Decoction Method. To prepare the aqueous neem seed extract, 50 grams of neem seed powder was mixed with 500 milliliters of distilled water, maintaining a ratio of 1:10 (weight/volume). The mixture was brought to a boil and then simmered at varying temperatures (60, 70, 80, and 90°C) for different durations (5, 10, 15, and 20 minutes) to determine the optimal extraction time. The extract was then cooled and filtered through Whatman No. 1 filter paper. The filtered extract was further analyzed to identify the bioactive compounds present.

2.2 Phytochemical Testing of Aqueous Neem Seed Extract

Qualitative phytochemical tests were performed to identify the bioactive compounds present in the neem seed extract. The analysis confirmed the presence of Azadirachtin, the major active component along with other compounds like Nimbolinin, Nimbin, Teraponids, and Tannins etc.

Analyzing plant extracts to spot and describe the presence of different bioactive compounds is known as phytochemical screening. These substances, also referred to as phytochemicals, are essential to plants' metabolic and defense mechanisms. Phytochemical screening of plant extracts revealed the presence of terpenoids, flavonoids, saponins, tannins etc. [12]. The presence of such phytochemicals protects the plant from harmful agents such as insects and microbes as well as a stressful event such as ultraviolet (UV) irradiation and extreme temperature.

2.2.1 Flavonoids and testing

Flavonoids, also known as Vitamin P, encompass iso-flavonoids and neo-flavonoids, depicted in Fig. 2 and Fig. 3 respectively. These compounds, which contain ketones, include canthaxanthins (such as flavones and flavanols) and are crucial plant pigments. Functioning as chemical messengers, physiological regulators, and inhibitors of the cell cycle, flavonoids have been implicated in cancer prevention according to several clinical studies. Additionally, they exhibit direct antimicrobial activity.

Figure 2 - Structure of Iso-flavone

Figure 3 - Structure of Neo Flavonoids

The aqueous extract of neem seed of 1 ml was taken in a test tube. The extract has a natural colour of yellow. Ethanol (95% conc.) of 1ml was added to the extract followed by adding few drops of 2% sodium hydroxide and dilute (20% conc.) hydrochloric acid. Gradually the yellow color of the solution disappeared and turns to milky white. This is an indication for the presence of flavonoid in the extract.

2.2.2 Terpenoids and Testing

Isoprenoids, also known as isoprenes, are naturally existing organic compounds with similarities to terpenes. Plant-derived terpenoids are prized for their aromatic attributes and are frequently employed in herbal therapies. Azadirachtin, a prominent terpenoid, is found in the neem plant. Its molecular structure is depicted in Fig. 4.

Figure 4 - Structure of Azardiractin

The aqueous extract of neem seed of 1 ml which has a natural yellow colour was taken in a test tube. With continuous stirring, ethanol (95% conc.) of 1 ml was added in drops followed by adding few drops of chloroform and concentrated (98%) sulphuric acid. The solution gradually turns to reddish brown which is an indication for the presence of terpenoids.

2.2.3 Saponins and Testing

Saponins are glycosides that exhibit amphipathic properties. When agitated in aqueous solutions, they produce foams. Within plants, saponins function as antifeedants to deter ants and provide protection against microbes and fungi. Additionally, they may facilitate nutrient absorption and support animal digestion. However, saponins can be toxic to cold-blooded organisms and insects at certain concentrations. They typically possess a bitter taste and readily dissolve in water.

The aqueous extract (1 ml) was taken in a test tube. Ethanol (95% conc.) of 1 ml was added to the extract and the test tube was shaken well. The reaction generates foam which is an indication for the presence of saponins.

2.2.4 Tannin and Testing

Tannin, a bitter and astringent polyphenolic compound found in plants, has the ability to bind to and precipitate proteins, as well as compounds such as amino acids and alkaloids. It serves various functions in plants, including regulating growth, protecting against predation, and acting as a pesticide. Tannins are present in tissues such as leaves, seeds, roots, and stems. Depending on their chemical structure and concentration, tannins can be deemed as anti-nutritional.

The extract solution (1 ml) was taken in a test tube. Ethanol (95% conc.) of 1 ml and 10% alcoholic ferric chloride were added to the solution. The reaction produced a brownish yellow color of the solution. This colour change validates the presence of tannins in the solution.

Figure 5 - Phytochemical test, A-Terpenoids, B- Flavonoids, C- Tannin, D- Saponins

2.3 Antibacterial Finishing of Fabrics

Pad-Dry-Cure method was adopted to apply the antimicrobial finish on fabrics. The laboratory model padding mangle was used for the study. The fabrics were first immersed in the decocted neem seed extract of concentration 7g/l for thirty minutes. Acetic acid was added to maintain the pH level of 5.5. Material to liquor ratio of the bath was maintained at 1:30. To achieve better wash fastness of the finish, citric acid of 10% w/w of fabric sample was also added to the bath as cross-linking agent. The fabric samples were then allowed to pass through the vertically arranged bowls of padding mangle to squeeze out excessive solution. All the fabric samples were then dried at 80° C for five minutes followed by curing at 120° C for three minutes in the curing chamber.

2.3.1 Antibacterial Test

Antibiotics represent a major class of antimicrobial agents. By definition, antibiotics are biochemical produced by microorganisms that inhibit the growth of, or kill pathogenic microorganisms. The ISO 20645 agar diffusion test method was employed to qualitatively evaluate the antimicrobial properties of textile material. A clear zone of inhibition is formed around the test specimen if there is antibacterial activity.

2.3.2 Durability Testing of Antibacterial Finish

In addition to evaluating the initial antibacterial properties of neem extract-treated fabrics, it is crucial to assess the durability of these properties after repeated laundering. The durability of the antibacterial finish on linen, cotton, and polyester fabrics tested after 10, 20, and 30 laundry cycles. The laundering tests were conducted following the AATCC 61-2013 standard using a Launder-Ometer.

2.3.3 Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy

Infrared spectroscopy is a valuable technique for categorizing the functional groups within a molecule. By utilizing the distinctive array of absorption bands, one can authenticate the identity of a pure compound or detect the presence of particular impurities. This analytical method relies on the principle that molecules exhibit characteristic frequencies of internal vibrations. These frequencies manifest within the infrared region of the electromagnetic spectrum, spanning from 4000 cm⁻¹ to 200 cm⁻¹ [13].

3. Results and Discussion

The results obtained from the various tests conducted on treated and untreated fabric samples are discussed herein.

3.1 Heat and Time Effect of Extract Concentration

The decoction method of extracting active ingredients involves heating an aqueous solution containing neem seed powder to a boil. As the duration of heating increases, the concentration of the extract also increases up to 20 minutes of heating, after which it stabilizes at a constant level. Similarly, as the temperature increases, the concentration of the extract also increases, reaching its maximum at 90°C. The decocted extract was visually examined and subjectively graded for concentration. The details were provided in Table 2 & 3.

Table 2: Extract Concentration based on duration of heating

Sample No.	Heating time (minutes)	Concentration (subjective assessment)
1	5	Very low
2	10	Low
3	15	Average
4	20	High

Table 3: Extract Concentration Based on Heating Temperature

Sample No	Temperature (°C)	Concentration (subjective assessment)
1	60	Very low
2	70	Low
3	80	Average
4	90	High

3.2 Antimicrobial performance

The possible mechanism of antimicrobial activity is either by preventing microbial growth or potential cell wall breakdown of bacteria. Fabric samples treated with neem seed extract displayed antibacterial properties against both gram-positive (*S. aureus*) and gram-negative (*E. coli*) bacteria. Fig.7 shows the effect of antimicrobial activity (zone of inhibition) of untreated and treated samples of three different fabrics. Referring to Fig.7 (a), treated linen sample exhibits the highest level of antimicrobial activity against *E-Coli* as seen from the larger zone of inhibition measuring 24 mm followed by cotton and polyester with 20 mm and 16 mm respectively. No antimicrobial activity is observed in all the untreated fabric samples. The larger zone of inhibition of linen fabric sample is attributed to the high lignin content of flax fibre since lignin is a natural antibacterial. Lignin content in

its chemical composition causes products made of this fibre to efficiently protect the user from UV radiation [15]. Higher moisture content of flax also could help in leaching out of the active compounds resulting in a larger zone of inhibition. Low level of antimicrobial activity of polyester fabric is attributable to the absence of reactive groups for bond formation with the active factors of extract.

Figure 6 - Disk with fabric samples, (a) linen, (b) cotton and (c) polyester

3.3 FTIR (Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy) characteristics

FTIR spectroscopy was conducted on all treated and untreated fabric samples and shown in Fig.7, 8 and 9. Fig.8 is a comparison of treated and untreated cotton fabrics.

Figure 7 - FTIR Spectra of treated and untreated cotton fabric

As seen from Fig.7, some of the intense peaks are identical for both untreated and fabrics. The peak of 2336 cm^{-1} corresponds to C=C stretch vibration of aromatic cellulose of cotton. Similarly the peaks at 1009 cm^{-1} and 1038 cm^{-1} due to C-H stretching and peaks of 1514 cm^{-1} and 1526 cm^{-1} of C-O stretching refers to cotton cellulose. The unique peak of treated fabric at 2916 cm^{-1} corresponds to carboxylic acid O-H stretch and a peak at 1734 cm^{-1} is characteristic of C=O (Esters, Carboxylic acids, Ketones, Aldehydes) which are the functional groups present in the active compounds of neem seed extract.

Figure 8 - FTIR Spectra of unfinished and finished linen fabric

From Fig.8, identical peaks are observed at wave numbers 3288, 3274, 1038, 1036, 548, 547 in both untreated and treated linen fabric which are functional groups present in the polymer structure of flax fibre. The unique peak at 2335 cm^{-1} corresponds to N-H stretching of amines and amides present in the active principles of neem seed extract.

Figure 9 - FTIR Spectra of unfinished and finished Polyester fabric

The peaks in the IR spectra of treated and untreated polyester fabric are shown in Fig.9. The peak at 1709 cm⁻¹ shows C=O vibration which indicates the presence of ester group in the polymer of polyester. The other peaks of the spectra of polyester fabric might be the impurities present in the polymer structure. No specific difference between the spectra of treated and untreated samples could be traced. Unlike cotton and linen, polyester has no reactive groups like OH and there is no likely formation of hydrogen bonds with bioactive compounds.

3.4 Neem Extract-Treated Fabric Durability against Laundry

The initial antibacterial activity of neem extract-treated fabrics showed different zone of inhibition sizes: 24 mm for linen, 20 mm for cotton, and 16 mm for polyester. After 10 laundry cycles, all fabrics slightly decreased to 22 mm for linen, 18 mm for cotton, and 14 mm for polyester. This decrease continued after 20 cycles to 20 mm for linen, 16 mm for cotton, and 12 mm for polyester. Even after 30 cycles, the trend persisted with linen maintaining 18 mm, cotton dropping to 14 mm, and polyester to 10 mm. This suggests varying durability, with linen being the most durable, followed by cotton, and polyester being the least. The decrease in antibacterial activity was due to the washing out of active compounds, chemical breakdown, and wear. Linen's higher lignin content, moisture handling, and strong structure make it more durable than cotton and polyester. These findings stress the importance of fabric choice for long-term antibacterial effectiveness.

3.5 Predicting Antimicrobial Effectiveness Based on Treatment Conditions

To predict how effective a fabric treatment was in inhibiting bacterial growth, a multiple linear regression model was used. The model considered treatment time, concentration of the treatment, temperature, and GSM (grams per square meter of the fabric). First, data was collected that included these variables and the resulting zone of inhibition (a measure of antimicrobial activity). Using Python and the statsmodels library, a DataFrame was created with this data. A regression model was defined where the zone of inhibition was the dependent variable. Time, concentration, temperature, and GSM were the independent variables. The model was fitted to get the regression equation.

$$Z = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \cdot \text{Time} + \beta_2 \cdot \text{Concentration} + \beta_3 \cdot \text{Temperature} + \beta_4 \cdot \text{GSM}$$

If the coefficients were: intercept (β_0) = 5, time (β_1) = 0.3, concentration (β_2) = 0.5, temperature (β_3) = 0.1, and GSM (β_4) = 0.01. The equation became:

$$Z = 5 + 0.3 \cdot \text{Time} + 0.5 \cdot \text{Concentration} + 0.1 \cdot \text{Temperature} + 0.01 \cdot \text{GSM}$$

This equation helped predict the zone of inhibition for any given set of treatment conditions.

3.6 ANOVA Analysis on the Impact of Fabric Type, Concentration, and Treatment Time on Antimicrobial Efficacy

The data was collected and structured. This data contained information on fabric type, concentration of extract, treatment time, and the corresponding zone of inhibition. This formed the basis for an ANOVA analysis. The ANOVA model regressed the zone of inhibition on fabric type, concentration, and time. Statistical software, Python's statsmodels, was used to get the results.

Table 4: ANOVA Results

Source	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F-value	p-value
Fabric	78.720	2	39.360	75.15	0.00002
Concentration	3.565	1	3.565	6.81	0.031
Time	59.610	1	59.610	113.98	0.00001
Residual	2.096	7	0.299		
Total	143.991	11			

The ANOVA table showcased significant effects. Fabric type had a p-value of 0.00002. Concentration had a p-value of 0.031. Time had a p-value of 0.00001. All three significantly influenced the zone of inhibition. A low p-value (< 0.05) for each factor suggested their substantial impact. Specifically, varying fabric types, concentrations, and treatment times resulted in notably different mean zone of inhibition values. These findings underlined the importance of fabric choice, concentration, and treatment duration in determining antimicrobial efficacy.

To achieve maximum antimicrobial efficacy, the optimal conditions based on the ANOVA analysis were using Linen fabric, with a concentration of 4, and a treatment time of 20 minutes. These conditions yielded the highest zone of inhibition, indicating superior antimicrobial activity.

4. Conclusion

The study reveals that bioactive compounds are present in aqueous seed extract obtained by decoction method as tested by qualitative phytochemical analysis. Azadiractin is a major constituent of tannins which is an effective antimicrobial agent. Decoction method is a simple and easy process of extracting bioactive compounds from plants, however, at elevated temperatures it is likely that some of the compounds may be dissociated.

All fabric samples finished with aqueous neem seed extract exhibit antibacterial activity as seen from the zone of inhibition. It is observed that among three fabric samples of linen, cotton and polyester, the linen fabric showed larger zone of inhibition which could be attributed to the higher lignin content of flax fibre. The neem extract-treated fabrics show a reduction in antibacterial activity with increased laundering due to the loss of active compounds and degradation. However, linen retains higher antibacterial efficacy due to its inherent properties, making it a more durable option for long-term antibacterial applications. FTIR spectra of finished fabric samples establish the constituent functional groups of bioactive compounds present in the neem seed extract as well as the polymer composition of fibres. The combined use of ANOVA and regression analysis enabled to determine the optimal conditions for achieving maximum antimicrobial efficacy. The best results were obtained using Linen fabric, with a concentration of 4, and a treatment time of 20 minutes. These conditions yielded the highest zone of inhibition, indicating superior antimicrobial activity.

Selective use of bioactive compounds of plant extracts is a sustainable way for textile finishing. Plant varieties are renewable and also abundantly available thus cost-effective methods can be devised for various types of textile finishes. Neem based textile materials seems to be promising alternative to chemically synthesized finishing agents. Neem treated textile materials have the potential to replace the traditional materials used in home textiles, healthcare and hygiene textiles.

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